

1 **Additional Information**

2 **Structural and Functional Characterization of a Highly Stable Endo- β -1-**
3 **4-xylanase from *Fusarium oxysporum* and Its Development as an**
4 **Efficient Immobilized Biocatalyst**

5 Sara Gómez¹, Asia M. Payne¹, Martin Savko², Gavin C. Fox², William E. Shepard², Francisco. J.
6 Fernandez^{1,3} and M. Cristina Vega^{1*}

7 * Correspondence: cvega@cib.csic.es.

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9 ¹ Structural and Quantitative Biology Department, Center for Biological Research (CIB-
10 CSIC), Madrid, Spain. E-mail: cvega@cib.csic.es

11 ² Synchrotron SOLEIL, Gif-sur-Yvette, France.

12 ³ Abvance SRL, Madrid, Spain.

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15 Additional Fig. 1. Schematic representation of Xyl2 topology. Strands are represented as
 16 arrow-headed rectangles, in pink, the α -helix is in blue, the 3_{10} A helix in cyan, and all
 17 connections are drawn as black lines.

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20 Additional Fig. 2. Docking of a xylose hexaoligosaccharide on Xyl2 (pH 5). This figure
 21 complements the docking results shown in Fig. 7 of the main text. The Xyl2 structure,
 22 represented as cartoon in orange, is that of the Xyl2/MBX crystal structure at 2.84 Å including
 23 the experimentally determined rotameric conformations of Tyr72 and Glu176 side chains. The
 24 hexasaccharide can be equally docked without loss of free energy or unfavorable interactions,
 25 despite the “flipped over” rotamers of the catalytic residues. Most of the interactions are
 26 established with the deepest bound section of the xylan chains (specifically, xylose subunit -2).

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29 Additional Fig. 3. **(a)** Schematic representation of rationale for random enzyme immobilization
 30 via the carrier or carrier-free approaches. Covalent binding (A, aminoethyl supports; B, glyoxal
 31 supports) and crosslinked enzyme aggregates (CLEAs). **(b)** Negative correlation between Xyl2
 32 activity yield and functionalization degree in high and low agarose supports. For visualization,
 33 supports with very high and very low functionalization degrees were discarded. The supports
 34 with low (AM-1, GL-1 and GL-3) or high (AM-2, AM-4, GL-2 and GL-4) functionalization degrees
 35 are depicted on two separate vertical lines intersecting an arbitrary horizontal coordinate, with
 36 the vertical axis representing the percent activity yield or residual activity. The negative
 37 correlation was calculated by linear regression ($R^2 = 0.9768$).

38 Additional Table 1. Guiding values for binding capacities of commercial agarose beads
 39 employed for Xyl2 immobilization.

Support	Matrix ¹	Functionalization degree ²	Binding capacity ³
Ni-Agarose resin	6%	6-18	≥15
Aminoethyl Low (AM-1)	6%	15-25	~14
Aminoethyl High (AM-2)	6%	40-60	~30
Aminoethyl Very low (AM-3)	4%	3-6	~5
Aminoethyl High (AM-4)	4%	40-60	~30
Glyoxal Low (GL-1)	4%	15-25	~10
Glyoxal High (GL-2)	4%	40-60	~20
Glyoxal Low (GL-3)	6%	15-25	~10
Glyoxal High (GL-4)	6%	40-60	~20
Glyoxal Very High (GL-5)	6%	80-100	~30

40 ¹ Agarose %; ² $\mu\text{mol Ni}^{2+}$, aminoethyl or glyoxyl /ml gel; ³ mg protein/ml gel.